

Fig. 3

Figure 3. Distance estimate for IRAS 19448-0234 from the Bayestar 2019 three-dimensional dust extinction map (Green et al. 2019). Upper panels: reddening profile extracted using the dustmaps Python package (v1.0; Green 2018) at the cloud coordinates ($\ell = 37.20^\circ$, $b = -13.58^\circ$, 0.5° beam). Top: cumulative reddening $E(B-V)$ as a function of distance (pc, log scale); the red dashed line marks the distance of maximum reddening gradient at ~ 200 pc. Bottom: derivative $dE(B-V)/dd$ (mag/pc), showing a sharp peak at ~ 200 pc that identifies the cloud front. No reddening is detected at distances shorter than ~ 160 pc, confirming a clean foreground sightline. Lower panel:

independent distance estimate from the same Bayestar 2019 dataset extracted via the Argonaut web interface (argonaut.skymaps.info) at the cloud coordinates ($l = 37.20^\circ$, $b = -13.58^\circ$). The y-axis shows cumulative reddening $E(g-r)$ in magnitudes; the x-axis shows distance modulus μ (mag), where $\mu = 5 \log(d/10 \text{ pc})$. The bold line shows the best-fit reddening profile; lighter lines show individual posterior samples. A sharp reddening onset at $\mu \approx 6.7 \text{ mag}$ ($d \approx 220 \text{ pc}$) identifies the cloud distance, with negligible reddening at shorter distances. The annotated values $d = 0.22 \text{ kpc}$ and $E(g-r) = 0.03 \text{ }^{+0.04}_{-0.03} \text{ mag}$ indicate the best-fit distance and the reddening contributed by the cloud. Shaded regions labelled 'No Stars' and 'No MS Stars' indicate distance ranges with insufficient stellar sampling to constrain the profile. The result is consistent with an independent extraction using the dustmaps Python package, which yields a reddening onset at $\sim 200 \text{ pc}$.